

Analysis of Customer's Impatience in Single Server Markovian Queuing Model

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to develop a model for a single server queue with Markovian features that accounts for customer impatience. We use the rate in rate out principle and the Markov process method to find the steady state probabilities. We obtain closed form expressions for both conventional and newly proposed measures. To illustrate the practical application of our results, a numerical example is provided. Sensitivity analysis using numerical techniques is conducted to explore how different performance measures change with variations in system parameters. Additionally, we perform cost analysis to examine how balking and reneging influence the expected profit using parabolic optimization technique. This research helps us to comprehend how impatience affects queue systems and offers useful guidance for optimizing their performance and cost.

Keywords: M/M/1, state dependent balking, reneging, Markovian, parabolic optimization.

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1 Introduction

In our everyday lives, we often find ourselves waiting in queue for various services. Queuing theory helps modeling such system and derive imperative performance metrics that illuminate the operational dynamics of queuing environment. With the help of these performance measures we can enhance the performance of queuing system which benefits customers by reducing waiting time for service and management by reducing operating costs and loss of business.

Customers make their own decisions of waiting in a queuing system where they have to wait. Customer might decide to join a queue if they expect a short wait, but if the wait becomes too long, they might give up and leave. This preceding customer, we call them impatient customer. Balking and reneging are two types of impatient behavior of customers.

When customers decide not to join a queue right when they arrive, it is called balking. Balking has two main categories: system independent and system dependent. System independent balking occurs when a customer chooses not to join the queue regardless of how many people are already in line. On the other hand, system dependent balking happens when a customer's choice to join or not is based on how many people are already waiting in the queue. In 1957, Haight(Haight, 1957) conducted early research into balking behavior, where he looked into the reason why customers might choose to balk. Anker and Gafarian(Anker Jr and Gafarian, 1963) were first to introduce Markovian reneging and balking on M/M/1/N queuing model.

Reneging refers to a situation where a customer initially joins a queue but later decides to leave the queue before receiving complete service. We can categorize reneging into two types viz. reneging until beginning of service (R.BOS) and reneging until end of service (R.EOS). In the case of R.BOS, customers can exit the queue at any time while they are waiting. However, once the service for a customer begins, they are no longer able to leave the queuing system. For example, a person waiting for his/her turn to visit doctor for checkup can leave only while waiting in Doctor's chamber but once checkup starts customer cannot leave. While in R.EOS, customer can leave the queuing system when waiting in queue as well as receiving service. For example, while downloading a file of big size from the internet a user may end the service i.e., leave the web page due to long wait time to download the file. Barrer(Barrer, 1957b)(Barrer, 1957a) carried out early work on reneging where he carried out the analysis considering deterministic reneging for single as well as multi- server Markovian queuing model.

Focusing on the aspects of customers' impatience, analysis of queuing models gets attention in most of the recent work. Bouchentouf and Yahiaoui (Bouchentouf and Yahiaoui, 2017), Bouchentouf et al. (Bouchentouf, Cherfaoui and Boualem, 2019)(Bouchentouf, Yahiaoui, Kadi and Majid, 2020) delved into single and multi-server Markovian queues, considering elements such as Bernoulli feedback, balking, reneging, customer retention, and server vacations. Swathi et al.(Swathi, Kumar and Rao, 2019) studied M/M/1 queues where customers decide not to join or leave the queue due to non-availability of server i.e., server vacation under single and multiple vacation policies. Srivastava et al. (Srivastava, Dwivedi, Rawat, Singh, Singh and Mishra, 2023) also investigated the M/M/1 queuing model, introducing elements like differentiated server vacations and a time-dependent reneging probability. Choudhury A and Medhi P (Choudhury and Medhi, 2011a) (Choudhury and Medhi, 2011b)(Pallabi and Choudhury, 2012) and Medhi P(Medhi, 2020) applied the concept of position-dependent reneging to both single-server and multiple-server Markovian queues, considering finite and infinite waiting space for customers. Ammar et.al(Ammar, El-Sherbiny, El-Shehawy and Al-Seedy, 2012) derived expressions for transient state probabilities for M/M/1/N queuing model with discouraged arrival and reneging using computable matrix technique.

Saikia G and Choudhury A (Saikia and Choudhury, 2021) delved into reverse balking in a single-server Markovian queue with a limited buffer. Som B.K. and Seth S (Som and Seth, 2023) focused on retention of impatient customers in single-server finite capacity queueing systems and modified reverse balking. Bouchentouf et al. (Bouchentouf, Boualem, Cherfaoui and Medjahri, 2021)dealt with mathematical analysis of Markovian multi-server queues having

a feedback mechanism and servers can take multiple breaks without retention. Bouchentouf et al. (Bouchentouf, Medjahri, Boualem and Kumar, 2022) addressed the mathematical modeling of multi-server Markovian queues with Bernoulli feedback under a multiple vacation policy without retention. Bouchentouf and Messabihi (Bouchentouf and Messabihi, 2018) performed analysis on non-homogeneous servers considering feedback, reverse balking, reneging and reverse balking. and Som and Kumar (Som and Kumar, 2018) studied heterogeneous server under reverse balking and reneging. Kumar and Sharma (Kumar and Sharma, 2012) studied multi-server finite buffer queue considering discourage arrival, reneging and retention of reneged customer. Some effective performance measures along with cost-profit analysis is performed.

There is no existing literature on stochastic analysis of single server Markovian queue where customers may leave the queue regardless of their position and may balk depending on the queue length with the waiting space being unlimited. At the same time, closed form expressions of various measures of effectiveness and cost analysis are also not available. Having some advance information about the potential business loss is crucial for any management so that they can implement some strategy to protect the revenue. This will be easier for practitioner's if they have proper & finite expression for various operating characteristics of a particular model. Thus, we try to provide the explicitly derived expression of conventional as well as freshly designed operating characteristics of a M/M/1 queuing model with the aforesaid assumptions.

This paper has the following structure: Section 2 explains the model's basic assumptions and Section 3 calculates steady state probabilities. Section 4 derives various performance metrics to analyze the model's operations. Section 5 shows a numerical example to illustrate the theoretical framework. Section 6 examines how the system responds to different parameters through a sensitivity analysis. Section 7 performs a cost analysis. Section 8 concludes the paper with key findings and implications. We have also included an appendix in Section 8 with detailed calculations to help the readers understand our research findings better

2 Assumption of model

We assume the following for the model:

1. Customer arrivals adhere to a Poisson distribution with a parameter α .
2. The reneging behavior follows a Poisson distribution with a parameter γ .
3. The reneging rate is assumed to follow Poisson law with parameter γ .
4. Balking probability is defined as $1 - \theta^n$ for state n .
5. The service discipline is FCFS (First come first serve).
6. A single server is employed.
7. The system is unbounded, allowing for an infinite number of customers..

3 Steady State Probabilities

Using the Markov process method, we find the steady state probabilities in this section. Initially, we examine the scenario where customers only renege from the queue. Let 'n' represent the state of the system, where n can take values 0, 1, 2, and so on. The following figure shows the state-transition diagram for the rule R_BOS:

Figure 1: State transition diagram under R_BOS

We designate ξ_n to represent the probability of having 'n' customers in the system. Through a recursive process, we derive the subsequent steady state equations:

$$\beta \xi_1 = \alpha \xi_0 \tag{3.1}$$

$$\alpha \theta^{n-1} \xi_{n-1} + (\beta + n\gamma) \xi_{n+1} = [\beta + (n-1)\gamma + \alpha \theta^n] \xi_n \quad n = 2, \dots \tag{3.2}$$

Solving for each n we get

From (3.1) we get

$$\xi_1 = \frac{\alpha}{\beta} \xi_0 \tag{3.3}$$

On solving we get

$$\xi_n = \frac{\alpha^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta + (r-1)\gamma\}} \xi_0 \tag{3.4}$$

Solving recursively we get

$$\xi_0 = \left[1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta + (r-1)\gamma\}} \right]^{-1} \tag{3.5}$$

Similarly, we now obtain the steady state probability under R_EOS and its transition diagram is given below:

Figure 2: State transition diagram under R_EOS

The probability of having 'n' customers in the system is denoted by η_n . The following are the steady state probabilities for the rule R_EOS:

$$(\beta + \nu) \eta_1 = \alpha \eta_0 \tag{3.6}$$

$$\{\beta + (n+1)\nu\} \eta_{n+1} + \alpha \theta^{n-1} \eta_{n-1} = [(\beta + n\gamma) + \alpha \theta^n] \eta_n \quad ; n = 1, 2, \dots \tag{3.7}$$

From equation (3.6) we get

$$\eta_1 = \frac{\alpha}{\beta + \gamma} \eta_0 \tag{3.8}$$

On solving recursively

$$\eta_n = \frac{\alpha^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n (\beta + r\gamma)} \eta_0 \tag{3.9}$$

where η_0 is obtained using normalizing condition and is given by

$$\eta_0 = \left[1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n (\beta + r\gamma)} \right]^{-1} \tag{3.10}$$

4 Performance Measures

A key performance measure in queuing theory is the mean number of customers in the system, which is represented by L. The calculation of L under both renegeing rules is elaborated in the appendix section. Various performance measures specific to each type of renegeing rule are presented below:

1. Mean system size

$$L_{R.BOS} = (1 - \xi_0) \left(1 - \frac{\beta}{\gamma} \right) + \frac{\alpha}{\gamma} P(\theta)$$

$$L_{R.EOS} = \frac{\alpha}{\gamma} Q(\theta) - \frac{\beta}{\gamma} (1 - \eta_0)$$

2. Mean queue size

$$\begin{aligned} L_{q(R.BOS)} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n-1) \xi_n \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n \xi_n - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \xi_n \\ &= L_{(R.BOS)} - (1 - \xi_0) \\ &= (1 - \xi_0) \left(1 - \frac{\beta}{\gamma} \right) + \frac{\alpha}{\gamma} P(\theta) - (1 - \xi_0) \\ &= \frac{\alpha}{\gamma} P(\theta) - (1 - \xi_0) \frac{\beta}{\gamma} \\ &= \frac{1}{\gamma} [\alpha P(\theta) - (1 - \xi_0) \beta] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} L_{q(R.EOS)} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n-1) \eta_n \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n \eta_n - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \eta_n \\ &= \frac{\alpha}{\gamma} Q(\theta) - \left(\frac{\beta}{\gamma} - 1 \right) (1 - \eta_0) \end{aligned}$$

3. **Mean waiting time in system** : It is obtained using the well known Little's law (D.Gross, 2008)

$$\begin{aligned} W_{R_BOS} &= \frac{L_{R_BOS}}{\alpha} \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha}(1 - \xi_0) \left(1 - \frac{\beta}{\gamma}\right) + \frac{1}{\gamma}P(\theta) \\ &= \frac{1}{\gamma} \left[(1 - \xi_0) \left(\frac{\gamma}{\alpha} - \frac{\beta}{\alpha}\right) + P(\theta) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} W_{R_EOS} &= \frac{L_{R_EOS}}{\alpha} \\ &= \frac{Q(\theta)}{\gamma} - \frac{\beta}{\alpha\gamma}(1 - \eta_0) \end{aligned}$$

4. **Mean waiting time in queue**: We obtain it by applying Little's law(D.Gross, 2008) under both the reneging rules

$$\begin{aligned} W_{q(R_BOS)} &= \frac{L_{q(R_BOS)}}{\alpha} \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha} \left[\frac{\alpha}{\gamma}P(\theta) - (1 - \xi_0)\frac{\beta}{\gamma} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{\gamma} \left[P(\theta) - (1 - \xi_0)\frac{\beta}{\alpha} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} W_{q(R_EOS)} &= \frac{L_{q(R_EOS)}}{\alpha} \\ &= \frac{Q(\theta)}{\gamma} - \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{\beta}{\gamma} - 1\right)(1 - \eta_0) \end{aligned}$$

5. **Effective arrival rate**: Customers arrive at the system with a rate denoted by α . However, some customers who arrive may not enter the system due to balking behaviour. Consequently, the initial arrival rate is different from the rate at which customers actually join the system due to balking behaviour. This modified rate, accounting for balking, is distinct for both reneging rules are given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{R_BOS}^e &= \alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \theta^n \xi_n \\ &= \alpha P(\theta) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{R_EOS}^e &= \alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \theta^n \eta_n \\ &= \alpha Q(\theta) \end{aligned}$$

6. **Average reneging rate**: We assumed that the patience time of each customer is exponentially distributed with a parameter γ . The rate at which customers leave the system

depends on both the system's current state and the specific reneging rule being considered. Following are the calculations of average reneging rate for both the rules:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Avg\ rr_{R.BOS} &= \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n\gamma\xi_n \\
 &= \gamma(L_{R.BOS} - \xi_1) \\
 &= (1 - \xi_0)(\gamma - \beta) + \alpha P(\theta) - \gamma\xi_1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 Avg\ rr_{R.EOS} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n\gamma\eta_n \\
 &= \gamma L_{R.EOS} \\
 &= \alpha Q(\theta) - \beta(1 - \eta_0)
 \end{aligned}$$

7. Average balking rate: We consider that the probability of customer balk is related to the state of the system. Hence, the average balking rate for both the rules where customers may leave the queue are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Avg\ balk_{R.BOS} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha(1 - \theta^n)\xi_n \\
 &= \alpha(1 - \xi_0) - \alpha[P(\theta) - \xi_0] \\
 &= \alpha[1 - P(\theta)]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 Avg\ balk_{R.EOS} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha(1 - \theta^n)\eta_n \\
 &= \alpha(1 - \eta_0) - \alpha[Q(\theta) - \eta_0] \\
 &= \alpha[1 - Q(\theta)]
 \end{aligned}$$

8. Mean rate of customer lost: Customers who balk or renege are lost opportunities for business in real situations. Management would be interested in knowing how much customer is lost on average. The formulas for the average customer loss for both the rules where are shown below. :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \alpha - \alpha_{(R.BOS)}^e + Avg\ rr_{(R.BOS)} &= \alpha - \alpha P(\theta) + (1 - \xi_0)(\gamma - \beta) + \alpha P(\theta) - \gamma\xi_1 \\
 &= \alpha + (1 - \xi_0)(\gamma - \beta) - \gamma\xi_1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \alpha - \alpha_{(R.EOS)}^e + avg\ rr_{(R.EOS)} &= \alpha - \alpha Q(\theta) + \alpha Q(\theta) - \beta(1 - \eta_0) \\
 &= \alpha - \beta(1 - \eta_0)
 \end{aligned}$$

9. **Proportion of customer lost:** For effective management decisions, it's important to understand the proportion of total customers who are lost, which provides insight into the overall business loss. This proportion is crucial for assessing the impact of customer impatience. The expression for both renegeing types are given below:

$$\frac{\alpha - \alpha_{R,BOS}^e + avg\ rr_{R,BOS}}{\alpha} = 1 + (1 - \xi_0) \left(\frac{\gamma - \beta}{\alpha} \right) - \frac{\gamma}{\alpha}$$

$$\frac{\alpha - \alpha_{R,EOS}^e + avg\ rr_{R,EOS}}{\alpha} = 1 - \frac{\beta}{\alpha} (1 - \eta_0)$$

10. **Actual server load:** The server only serves the customers who are still in the queue . Customers who leave the queue do not get the service from the server. This provide a measure for actual load in the server which is denoted by α^s . The expression for both renegeing types are given below::

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{R,BOS}^s &= \alpha_{R,BOS}^e \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n\gamma\xi_n}{\alpha_{R,BOS}^e} \right) \\ &= \alpha_{R,BOS}^e - Avg\ rr_{R,BOS} \\ &= \alpha P(\theta) - (1 - \xi_0)(\gamma - \beta) - \alpha P(\theta) + \gamma\xi_1 \\ &= \gamma\xi_1 - (1 - \xi_0)(\gamma - \beta) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{R,EOS}^s &= \alpha_{R,EOS}^e \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n\gamma\xi_n}{\alpha_{R,BOS}^e} \right) \\ &= \alpha_{R,EOS}^e - Avg\ rr_{R,EOS} \\ &= \alpha Q(\theta) - \alpha Q(\theta) + \beta(1 - \eta_0) \\ &= \beta(1 - \eta_0) \end{aligned}$$

5 Numerical example

To illustrate the usefulness of our derived results, we consider the following example from (Ravindran and Solberg, 1987, p. 338). *“It concerns a grain elevator at a small town in one of the plains states where wheat is the principal crop. During the harvest season, trucks loaded with wheat from the fields arrive at the elevator, where they must quickly deposit their load and return to fields for another. The check in process involves weighing the truck, drawing samples for moisture and contamination tests, and a few other details before the load can be dumped through a grate. The farmers are very concerned about getting their crop off the field and into the elevator quickly. Once the wheat is ripe, it is highly vulnerable to rain or wind. Any delay could threaten a significant portion of a farmer’s income for the whole year. Of course, all of the fields in a region ripen about the same time, so it is not surprising that a traffic problem could develop at the elevator. The average interarrival time is estimated to be 9/hr, further 10 trucks are serviced on the average.”*

The problem’s nature makes us expect that balking and renegeing as likely reactions due to the problem’s characteristics. Protecting crops from possible harm is the main priority of the farmers. Consequently, the level of impatience in farmer will have an effect in queue. Our model’s

assumptions are structured to capture this real-world scenario effectively. Specifically, We will set the reneging rate $\gamma=2/\text{hr}$ and compare two cases with different probability of joining the queue θ viz: $\theta=0.9$ and $\theta=0.5$. We used a Python program that we carefully created to calculate various performance indicators based on these parameters. The table below shows the results clearly.:

Table 1: Performance measures when $\alpha = 9, \beta = 10, \gamma = 2$

Performance measures	Balking probability	
	0.1	0.5
Mean queue length	0.622682	0.1994657
Mean waiting time in queue	0.069187	0.0221628
Effective arrival rate	7.923531	6.0429157
Mean reneging rate	1.983067	0.7436455
Proportion of customer lost due balking and reneging	0.41415	0.4739031
Actual server load	5.940463	5.299271

From the table we can make the following observations:

As the balking probability increases mean queue length, mean waiting time in queue, effective arrival rate, average reneging rate and actual server load decreases. The effective arrival rate decreases as more customers balk and do not join the system. If less customer arrive the system less customer will form queue and hence a customer has to wait less in queue for service and also less customer will renege. Also if there are less customer's in queue actual server load will decrease. As balking probability increases, proportion of customer loss due to balking and reneging increases .

6 Sensitivity analysis

We want to explore how the system's different aspects vary when we modify its main features in this section.. To do this, we'll perform sensitivity analysis. To keep things clear, we'll use a specific way of writing things for the rest of this section. The probability of having 'n' customers in the system in steady state under the rule R.BOS is denoted by $\xi_n(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$. Similarly, $\eta_n(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ for R.EOS. Using this notation, we can learn how the system acts under different situations and how it adapts to variations in its parameters.

1. Let $\alpha_1 > \alpha_0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\xi_0(\alpha_1, \beta, \gamma)}{\xi_0(\alpha_0, \beta, \gamma)} &< 1 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\left[1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha_1^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta + (r-1)\gamma\}}\right]^{-1}}{\left[1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha_0^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta + (r-1)\gamma\}}\right]^{-1}} &< 1 \\ \Rightarrow 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha_1^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta + (r-1)\gamma\}} &> 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha_0^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta + (r-1)\gamma\}} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\alpha_1}{\beta} + \frac{\alpha_1^2 \theta}{\beta(\beta + \gamma)} + \frac{\alpha_1^3 \theta^3}{\beta(\beta + \gamma)(\beta + 2\gamma)} + \dots &> \frac{\alpha_0}{\beta} + \frac{\alpha_0^2 \theta}{\beta(\beta + \gamma)} + \frac{\alpha_0^3 \theta^3}{\beta(\beta + \gamma)(\beta + 2\gamma)} + \dots \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\alpha_1 - \alpha_0}{\beta} + \frac{(\alpha_1^2 - \alpha_0^2)\theta}{\beta(\beta + \gamma)} + \frac{\alpha_1^3 - \alpha_0^3 \theta^3}{\beta(\beta + \gamma)(\beta + 2\gamma)} + \dots &> 1 \end{aligned}$$

which is true. Hence ξ_0 decreases as α increases.

2. Let $\beta_1 > \beta_0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\xi_0(\alpha, \beta_1, \gamma)}{\xi_0(\alpha, \beta_0, \gamma)} &< 1 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\left[1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta_1 + (r-1)\gamma\}}\right]^{-1}}{\left[1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta_0 + (r-1)\gamma\}}\right]^{-1}} &< 1 \\ \Rightarrow 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta_1 + (r-1)\gamma\}} &< 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta_0 + (r-1)\gamma\}} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\alpha}{\beta_1} + \frac{\alpha^2 \theta}{\beta_1(\beta_1 + \gamma)} + \frac{\alpha^3 \theta^3}{\beta_1(\beta_1 + \gamma)(\beta_1 + 2\gamma)} + \dots &< \frac{\alpha}{\beta_0} + \frac{\alpha^2 \theta}{\beta_0(\beta_0 + \gamma)} + \frac{\alpha^3 \theta^3}{\beta_0(\beta_0 + \gamma)(\beta_0 + 2\gamma)} + \dots \\ \Rightarrow \alpha \left(\frac{1}{\beta_1} - \frac{1}{\beta_0} \right) + \alpha^2 \theta \left[\frac{1}{\beta_1(\beta_1 + \gamma)} - \frac{1}{\beta_0(\beta_0 + \gamma)} \right] + \alpha^3 \theta^3 & \\ & \left[\frac{1}{\beta_1(\beta_1 + \gamma)(\beta_1 + 2\gamma)} - \frac{1}{\beta_0(\beta_0 + \gamma)(\beta_0 + 2\gamma)} \right] < 0 \end{aligned}$$

which is true since $\beta_1 > \beta_0 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{\beta_1} < \frac{1}{\beta_0}$. Hence ξ_0 increases as β increases.

3. Let $\gamma_1 > \gamma_0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\xi_0(\alpha, \beta, \gamma_1)}{\xi_0(\alpha, \beta, \gamma_0)} &< 1 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\left[1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta + (r-1)\gamma_1\}}\right]^{-1}}{\left[1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta + (r-1)\gamma_0\}}\right]^{-1}} &< 1 \\ \Rightarrow 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta + (r-1)\gamma_1\}} &< 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^n \theta^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{\prod_{r=1}^n \{\beta + (r-1)\gamma_0\}} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\alpha}{\beta} + \frac{\alpha^2 \theta}{\beta(\beta + \gamma_1)} + \frac{\alpha^3 \theta^3}{\beta(\beta + \gamma_1)(\beta + 2\gamma_1)} + \dots &< \frac{\alpha}{\beta} + \frac{\alpha^2 \theta}{\beta(\beta + \gamma_0)} + \frac{\alpha^3 \theta^3}{\beta(\beta + \gamma_0)(\beta + 2\gamma_0)} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\alpha^2\theta}{\beta} \left(\frac{1}{\beta + \gamma_1} - \frac{1}{\beta + \gamma_0} \right) + \frac{\alpha^3\theta^3}{\beta} \left[\frac{1}{(\beta + \gamma_1)(\beta + 2\gamma_1)} - \frac{1}{(\beta + \gamma_0)(\beta + 2\gamma_0)} \right] + \dots < 0$$

which is true since $\gamma_1 > \gamma_0 \Rightarrow \beta + \gamma_1 > \beta + \gamma_0 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{\beta + \gamma_1} < \frac{1}{\beta + \gamma_0}$. Hence ξ_0 increases as γ increases.

We look at how the performance measure changes when we alter the value of parameters. The results are shown in tables and graphs below.

Table 2: Variation of L, W, α^e , Proportion of customer lost (PCL) and α^s w.r.t. α considering ($\beta = 9, \gamma = 2, \theta = 0.98$)

α	L	W	α^e	Avg rr	PCL	α^s
9	1.557454	0.1730504	8.725278	2.577241	0.316884	6.1480374
10	1.822282	0.1822282	9.643869	3.144391	0.350052	6.259465
11	2.104385	0.1913078	10.548942	3.752318	0.382125	6.365696
12	2.402337	0.2001948	11.439964	4.395262	0.412941	6.466860
13	2.714437	0.208802	12.316588	5.067381	0.442368	6.5630896
14	3.038796	0.2170568	13.178657	5.762965	0.470307	6.6545203

Figure 3: Impact of α on performance measures

The data presented in Table 2 reveals a notable trend: as the arrival rate α increases, all the considered operating characteristics tend to increase. However, an exception arises with respect to the actual server load α_s , which remains relatively constant. This observation underscores that while an increase in the arrival rate influences various aspects of the system, it has a limited impact on the actual server load α_s . This suggests that higher arrival rates do not significantly affect the workload on the server, highlighting the distinct behavior of this particular performance measure.

The rationale underlying increment of other operational characteristics can be attributed to the following phenomenon: as the influx of customers intensifies, the queue length progressively extends, culminating in prolonged service waiting times for individual customers. Subsequently, the tendency for customers to abandon the queue and renege escalates. This causal relationship is further substantiated through graphical representation, where the interplay between arrival rates, queue length, and renege tendencies becomes clearly evident.

Table 3: Variation of L, W, α^e , Proportion of customer lost (PCL) and α^s w.r.t. β considering ($\alpha = 10, \gamma = 2, \theta = 0.98$)

β	L	W	α^e	Avg rr	PCL	α^s
10	1.557454	0.173050	8.72527	2.577241	0.3168847	6.148037
11	1.395685	0.155076	8.753440	2.239020	0.276175	6.514420
12	1.258024	0.139781	8.77745	1.955261	0.2419778	6.822198
13	1.140486	0.126721	8.798001	1.716684	0.213186	7.081325
14	1.039679	0.115519	8.815664	1.515392	0.1888585	7.300272
15	0.952775	0.105863	8.83091	1.344814	0.168211	7.486095

Figure 4: Impact of β on performance measures

With an increase in β , we observe a consistent decline across all performance measures, with one exception: the actual server load, represented as α^s , experiences an upward trajectory. Concurrently, the effective arrival rate demonstrates relatively marginal changes.

The rationale behind the amplified value of actual server load α^s can be attributed to the fact that as the service rate intensifies, the server’s workload escalates proportionally. Meanwhile, the effective arrival rate remains relatively stable due to its dependence solely on the arrival rate. The augmented service rate leads to reduced customer waiting times, resulting in a decreased number of customer’s waiting for service. Consequently, this reduction in wait times corresponds to a decrease in the tendency for customer to renege which is evident from behavior of mean renege rate. This intricate relationship between service rate, customer wait times, and renege tendencies is further elucidated through graphical representation.

Table 4: Variation of L, L_q , W, W_q , α^e , Avg rr, Average customer lost , Proportion of customer lost (PCL) and α^s w.r.t. γ considering ($\alpha = 10, \beta = 10, \theta = 0.98$)

γ	L	W	α^e	Avg rr	PCL	α^s
2	1.557454	0.1730504	8.725278	2.577241	0.3168847	6.148037
3	1.347706	0.1497452	8.7614312	3.163040	0.377956	5.305030
4	1.21525	0.135027	8.784392	3.615038	0.425627	4.5463692
5	1.12204	0.124671	8.800609	3.981570	0.464551	3.841849
6	1.05201	0.116890	8.8128263	4.288076	0.49725	3.17539
7	0.997041	0.1107824	8.822436	4.549895	0.525273	2.53725

Figure 5: Impact of γ on performance measures

We observe a clear correlation: as the reneging rate γ escalates, both the average reneging rate and the proportion of lost customers witness a proportional increase, which is an intuitive outcome. Conversely, as γ surges, more customers opt to abandon the queue, leading to a reduction in the mean system size and consequently a decrease in the mean waiting time within the system. As customers exit the system, the server’s workload diminishes, resulting in a decline in the actual server load. This pattern highlights a reciprocal relationship between the reneging rate γ and various key performance metrics, underscoring the intricate dynamics at play in the queuing system.

7 Cost analysis

Here we examine the cost for the model under R_BOS. For this we first define some cost elements which are given below:

C_L : Cost of holding customer per unit time

C_{ser} : Service cost per unit time

C_{balk} : Cost due to balking of customer per unit time

C_{renee} : Cost due to reneging of customer per unit time

C_{fix} : fixed expense of server per unit.

R: Revenue gained by providing service per customer

We define the expected cost as a function of reneging rate which is given below:

$$EC = g(\gamma) = L_{R_BOS}C_L + \mu C_{ser} + Avg\ rr_{R_BOS}C_{renee} + Avg\ balk_{R_BOS}C_{balk} + C_{fix} \quad (7.1)$$

We now fix the cost elements as $C_L = 4$, $C_{ser} = 9$, $C_{renee} = 3$, $C_{balk} = 2$ and $C_{fix} = 2$ in equation (7.1) to obtain the minimum cost using parabolic interpolation method. In this method, we first select three points near to the extreme points over an interval of $g(\gamma)$ and fit a parabola to those three points iteratively. The point at which $g(x)$ is minimum of the three points $\{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$ is given by

$$x_{min} = \frac{0.5(x_2^2 - x_3^2)g(x_1)(x_3^2 - x_1^2)g(x_2)(x_1^2 - x_2^2)g(x_3)}{(x_2 - x_3)g(x_1)(x_3 - x_1)g(x_2)(x_1 - x_2)g(x_3)} \quad (7.2)$$

One of three points having maximum value of $g(x)$ is replaced by x_{min} obtained in equation (7.2)(Hassoun and Abdel-Wahed, 2006). These step is repeated under a desired level of precision is achieved.

On applying the parabolic interpolation technique corresponding to $\gamma = 0.7751$, the optimal cost = 105.7397. Figure below verified the observed result

Figure 6: Operating cost per unit of time vs reneging rate

The queuing system's overall revenue generated through customer service is outlined as follows:

$$Total\ revenue = R\mu(1 - \xi_0) \tag{7.3}$$

We fix the value of $R=20$ and use the optimal value $\gamma = 0.7751$ in equation (7.3) so that Total revenue=151.1599

The total expected profit is given by

$$\begin{aligned} Total\ profit &= Total\ revenue - EC \\ &= 45.413 \end{aligned}$$

8 Conclusion

This research conducts an in-depth examination of a Markovian queuing system with a single server. It considers the dynamics of state-dependent balking, taking into account two reneging rules: reneging until the beginning of service (R_BOS) and reneging until the end of service (R_EOS). While prior research has touched upon balking & reneging but we went a step further by furnishing explicit expression encompassing both reneging rules. This paper established closed for expression for a range of traditional and innovative performance measures, enhancing our understanding of system behavior. To investigate how different performance metrics respond to alterations in system parameters, a comprehensive sensitivity analysis is conducted. We use a practical example for showcasing the practical applicability of our theoretical framework. To examine the influence of balking and reneging on anticipated profit, a cost analysis has been carried out specifically regarding the reneging rate, utilizing a parabolic op-

timization technique. Furthermore, derived outcomes can be extended to encompass general distribution.

9 Appendix

9.1 Calculation of $P'(1)$ under R_BOS

From equation (3.2) we have

$$\alpha\theta^{n-1}\xi_{n-1} + (\beta + n\gamma)\xi_{n+1} = [\beta + (n - 1)\gamma + \alpha\theta^n]\xi_n$$

Multiplying both sides by s^n and taking summation from 2 to ∞ we get

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \alpha \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^{n-1} \xi_{n-1} s^n + \beta \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \xi_{n+1} s^n + \gamma \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n \xi_{n+1} s^n &= \beta \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \xi_n s^n + \gamma \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (n-1) \xi_n s^n + \alpha \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \xi_n s^n \\ \Rightarrow \alpha s \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^{n-1} \xi_{n-1} s^{n-1} + \frac{\beta}{s} \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \xi_{n+1} s^{n+1} + \gamma \left[\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (n+1) \xi_{n+1} s^n - \frac{1}{s} \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \xi_{n+1} s^{n+1} \right] &= \beta \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \xi_n s^n + \\ &\gamma \left[s \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n \xi_n s^{n-1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \xi_n s^n \right] + \alpha \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \xi_n s^n \\ \Rightarrow \alpha s^2 \theta \xi_1 + \alpha s \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \xi_n s^n + \frac{\beta}{s} [P(s) - \xi_0 - \xi_1 s - \xi_2 s^2] + \nu [P'(s) - \xi_1 - 2\xi_2 s - \frac{1}{s} \{P(s) - \xi_0 - \xi_1 s - \xi_2 s^2\}] &= \\ \beta [P(s) - \xi_0 - \xi_1 s] + \gamma [s \{P'(s) - p_1\} - \{P(s) - \xi_0 - \xi_1 s\}] + \alpha (1-s) \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \xi_n s^n & \\ \Rightarrow \alpha s^2 \theta \xi_1 + \frac{\beta P(s)}{s} - \frac{\beta \xi_0}{s} - \beta \xi_1 - \beta \xi_2 s + \gamma P'(s) - \gamma \xi_2 s - \frac{\gamma P(s)}{s} + \frac{\gamma \xi_0}{s} = \beta P(s) - \beta \xi_0 - \beta \xi_1 s + \gamma s P'(s) & \\ - \gamma P(s) + \gamma \xi_0 + \alpha (1-s) \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \xi_n s^n & \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\beta P(s)}{s} - \frac{\gamma \xi_0}{s} - \beta P(s) + \gamma P(s) + [\gamma P'(s) - \gamma s P'(s)] = \frac{\beta \xi_0}{s} + \beta \xi_0 + \beta \xi_2 s + \gamma \xi_2 s - \frac{\gamma \xi_0}{s} - \beta \xi_0 - \beta \xi_1 s + \gamma \xi_0 + & \\ \alpha (1-s) \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \xi_n s^n - \alpha s^2 \theta \xi_1 & \\ \Rightarrow (1-s)P(s) \left(\frac{\alpha}{s} - \frac{\gamma}{s} \right) + \gamma P'(s)(1-s) = (1-s) \left[\frac{\alpha \xi_0}{s} + \beta \xi_1 - \frac{\gamma \xi_0}{s} \right] + [\beta \xi_2 s + \gamma \xi_2 s - \alpha s^2 \theta \xi_1] + & \\ \alpha (1-s) [P(\theta) - \xi_0 - \theta \xi_1 s] \quad [where P(\theta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \xi_n \theta^n] & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow (1-s)P(s) \left(\frac{\alpha}{s} - \frac{\gamma}{s} \right) + \gamma P'(s)(1-s) &= (1-s) \left[\frac{\alpha\xi_0}{s} + \beta\xi_1 - \frac{\gamma\xi_0}{s} \right] + [\beta s \frac{\alpha^2\theta\xi_0}{\beta(\beta+\gamma)} + \gamma s \frac{\alpha^2\theta\xi_0}{\beta(\beta+\gamma)} \\ &\quad - \alpha s^2\theta \frac{\alpha}{\beta}\xi_0] + \alpha(1-s)[P(\theta) - \xi_0 - \theta\xi_1s] \\ \Rightarrow P(s) \left(\frac{\beta}{s} - \frac{\gamma}{s} \right) + \gamma P'(s) &= \frac{\beta\xi_0}{s} + \beta\xi_1 - \frac{\gamma\xi_0}{s} + \frac{\alpha^2s\theta\xi_0}{\beta} + \alpha[P(\theta) - \xi_0 - \theta\xi_1s] \end{aligned}$$

Taking limit as $s \rightarrow 1$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \beta - \gamma + \gamma P'(1) &= \alpha\xi_0 + \alpha\xi_1 - \gamma\xi_0 + \frac{\alpha^2\theta\xi_0}{\beta} + \alpha P(\theta) - \alpha\xi_0 - \alpha\theta\xi_1 \\ \Rightarrow \gamma P'(1) &= \gamma - \alpha + \alpha\xi_0 + \alpha\xi_1 - \gamma\xi_0 + \frac{\alpha^2\theta\xi_0}{\beta} + \alpha P(\theta) - \alpha\xi_0 - \alpha\theta\xi_1 \\ \Rightarrow P'(1) &= 1 - \frac{\beta}{\gamma} + \frac{\beta\xi_0}{\gamma} - \xi_0 + \frac{\alpha P(\theta)}{\gamma} \\ &= (1 - \xi_0) - \frac{\beta}{\gamma}(1 - \xi_0) + \frac{\alpha}{\gamma}P(\theta) \\ L_{R.BOS} &= (1 - \xi_0) \left(1 - \frac{\beta}{\gamma} \right) + \frac{\alpha}{\gamma}P(\theta) \end{aligned}$$

9.2 Calculation of $Q'(s)$ under R_EOS

From equation (3.7) we have

$$\{\beta + (n + 1)\gamma\}\eta_{n+1} + \alpha\theta^{n-1}\eta_{n-1} = [(\beta + n\gamma) + \alpha\theta^n]\eta_n$$

Multiplying both sides by s^n and summing from 2 to ∞ we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [\{\beta + (n + 1)\gamma\}\eta_{n+1} + \alpha\theta^{n-1}\eta_{n-1}]s^n &= \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [(\beta + n\gamma) + \alpha\theta^n]\eta_n s^n \\ \Rightarrow \beta \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \eta_{n+1}s^n + \gamma \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (n + 1)\eta_{n+1}s^n + \alpha \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^{n-1}\eta_{n-1}s^n &= \beta \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \eta_n s^n + \gamma \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n\eta_n s^n + \alpha \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \eta_n s^n \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\beta}{s} \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \eta_{n+1}s^{n+1} + \gamma \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (n+1)\eta_{n+1}s^n + \alpha s \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^{n-1}\eta_{n-1}s^{n-1} &= \beta \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \eta_n s^n + \gamma s \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n\eta_n s^{n-1} + \\ &\quad \alpha \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \eta_n s^n \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\beta}{s} [Q(s) - \eta_0 - \eta_1s - \eta_2s^2] + \gamma [Q'(s) - \eta_1 - 2\eta_2s] + \alpha s^2\theta\eta_1 &= \beta [Q(s) - \eta_0 - \eta_1s] + \gamma s [Q'(s) - \eta_1] + \\ &\quad \alpha(1-s) \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \eta_n s^n \\ \Rightarrow Q(s) \frac{\beta}{s} (1-s) + \gamma(1-s)Q'(s) &= \alpha(1-s) \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \eta_n s^n + \eta_0 \frac{\beta}{s} (1-s) + \eta_1(1-s)(\beta + \gamma) + \\ &\quad (\beta s\eta_2 + 2\gamma s\eta_2 - \alpha s^2\theta\eta_1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow Q(s)\frac{\beta}{s}(1-s) + \gamma(1-s)Q'(s) = \alpha(1-s) \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \eta_n s^n + \eta_0 \frac{\beta}{s}(1-s) + \eta_1(1-s)(\beta + \gamma) +$$

$$\left[\beta s \frac{\alpha^2 \theta \eta_0}{(\beta + \gamma)(\beta + 2\gamma)} + 2\gamma s \frac{\alpha^2 \theta \eta_0}{(\beta + \gamma)(\beta + 2\gamma)} - \alpha s^2 \theta \frac{\alpha \eta_0}{\beta + \gamma} \right] \quad [Using (8) \& (9)]$$

$$\Rightarrow Q(s)\frac{\beta}{s}(1-s) + \gamma(1-s)Q'(s) = \alpha(1-s) \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \eta_n s^n + \eta_0 \frac{\beta}{s}(1-s) + \eta_1(1-s)(\beta + \gamma) +$$

$$\frac{\alpha^2 \theta \eta_0}{\beta + \gamma} s(1-s)$$

$$\Rightarrow Q(s)\frac{\beta}{s} + \gamma Q'(s) = \alpha \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \eta_n s^n + \frac{\beta \eta_0}{s} + \eta_1(\beta + \gamma) + \frac{\alpha^2 \theta \eta_0 s}{\beta + \gamma}$$

Taking limit as $s \rightarrow 1$ in both sides we get

$$\beta + \gamma Q'(1) = \alpha \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \theta^n \eta_n + \beta \eta_0 + \eta_1(\beta + \gamma) + \frac{\alpha^2 \theta \eta_0}{\beta + \gamma}$$

$$\Rightarrow \gamma Q'(1) = \alpha \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \theta^n \eta_n - \eta_0 - \eta_1 \theta \right] - \beta(1 - \eta_0) + (\beta + \gamma) \frac{\alpha}{\beta + \gamma} \eta_0 + \frac{\alpha^2 \theta \eta_0}{\beta + \gamma} \quad [Using (8)]$$

$$= \alpha Q(\theta) - \alpha \eta_0 - \alpha \theta \frac{\alpha \eta_0}{\beta + \gamma} - \beta(1 - \eta_0) + \alpha \eta_0 + \frac{\alpha^2 \theta \eta_0}{\beta + \gamma} \quad [Q(\theta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \theta^n \eta_n]$$

$$= \alpha Q(\theta) - \beta(1 - \eta_0)$$

$$\Rightarrow Q'(1) = L_{R_EOS} = \frac{\alpha}{\gamma} Q(\theta) - \frac{\beta}{\gamma} (1 - \eta_0)$$

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